

THREE-DIMENSIONAL CONSTITUTIVE MODEL OF SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER COMPOSITES CONSIDERING RATE-DEPENDENT BEHAVIOUR

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotube-reinforced shape memory polymer composites (CNT-SMPCs) have been widely studied in many fields because of their high mechanical properties and thermal conductivity. Theoretical models have been developed to understand the thermo-mechanical behaviour of shape memory polymer (SMP). Most constitutive models developed for SMPs are based on phenomenological models that can describe the thermo-mechanical deformation behaviour of SMPs using a continuum element. In this study, we developed a new three-dimensional constitutive model for simulating the shape memory behavior of SMPs and CNT-SMPCs considering temperature rate dependency.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) can ‘memorize’ their initial shape and return to it with the aid of an external stimulus from their temporary deformed shape. SMPs have been studied in a variety of research fields such as biomedicine and robotics due to their several merits over shape memory alloys (SMAs), including high deformability and recovery ratio and low weight. However, the mechanical properties and thermal conductivity of SMPs are relatively poor than those of shape memory polymer composites (SMPCs). Carbon nanotube-reinforced shape memory polymer composites (CNT-SMPCs) have been developed to overcome these disadvantages [1].

Theoretical models have been researched to describe the thermomechanical behaviour of SMPs. Most of the constitutive models for SMPs that have been developed are phenomenological model using a continuum element [2,3]. To simulate the shape memory effect of an SMP, Park et al. [1] developed a three-dimensional (3D) constitutive equation using the multiplicative decomposition of total deformation. However, the resulting 3D constitutive equation of SMP was limited in its ability to accurately predict the mechanical behavior of SMPs and CNT-SMPCs under different mechanical and temperature rate conditions. To overcome these limitations, Boyce [4] suggested a rate-dependent constitutive model for glassy polymers. This model contains two rheological components based on the macromolecular structure of the material and the micro-mechanism of plastic flow, which encompass the rate dependencies of glassy polymers. For thermally induced rate dependent behaviour of SMPs and SMPCs, M. Lei et al. developed the 1-D constitutive model considering thermal effects which have different behaviour at cooling and heating conditions [5], and Noll [6] suggested thermal deformation gradient tensor assuming SMP as thermally isotropic material.

In this study, we developed a new 3D constitutive model combining previously developed 3D constitutive model with the Arruda-Boyce model and thermally induced components [4] and analysed the shape memory performance of SMPs and CNT-SMPCs under different rate conditions. CNT-SMPCs were prepared with an epoxy SMP resin and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). The mechanical properties and shape memory performance of SMPs and CNT-SMPCs were characterized at different strain and temperature rates, and a self-deployable 3D antenna was fabricated and tested to

verify the constitutive model. Finally, shape memory performances of the self-deployable 3D antenna were simulated and compared with the experimental results.

2 CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

A three-dimensional constitutive model was developed to predict the thermomechanical behaviour of SMPs and SMPCs under different rate conditions. This model is composed of rubbery, glassy, and thermal strain components as shown in Figure 1. The rubbery phase consists of the Mooney-Rivlin spring and a spring-dashpot element for analysing the viscoelastic behaviour of SMPs and SMPCs at high temperature [1]. The glassy phase contains additional viscoplastic element for non-recoverable deformation and a non-mechanical strain component [1,3]. To consider the thermal deformation, thermally isotropic material behaviour was assumed for SMPs and SMPCs following Noll's theorem [4]. Finally, the volume fraction of the glassy phase was determined by storage modulus data under different temperature rates. Detailed mathematical equations were listed in Table 1, and were implemented into COMSOL software.

Figure 1: Constitutive model for SMPs and SMPCs

Table 1: Governing equations for constitutive model

Governing equation		
Rubbery phase	Mooney-Rivlin hyperelastic spring	$\mathbf{S}_r = f_{s_r}(\mathbf{C}_r^v, \mathbf{F}, \mathbf{I})$ [16]
	Newtonian fluid	$k_r \dot{\mathbf{C}}_r^v = f_{c_r}(\mathbf{C}_r^v, \mathbf{F}, \mathbf{I}), \phi_r = \frac{1}{2} k_r \dot{\mathbf{C}}_r^v : \dot{\mathbf{C}}_r^v$ [16]
Glassy phase	Hyperelastic spring	$\mathbf{T}_g^e = \frac{1}{\det[\mathbf{F}_e]} [\Lambda tr(\mathbf{h}) \mathbf{I} + 2\mathbf{G}\mathbf{h}]$ [17]
	Langevin spring	$\mathbf{T}_g^b = \frac{1}{3} C_r \sqrt{N} \zeta^{-1} \left[\frac{\Lambda_{chain}^p}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{(\Lambda_{p,g}^p)^2 - \frac{1}{3} \mathbf{I}_1}{\Lambda_{chain}^p} \right]$ [17]
	Viscoplasticity	$\dot{\mathbf{F}}_g^{vp} = \dot{\gamma}_p \mathbf{M}\mathbf{F}_p$ [17]

	Non-mechanical strain	$\frac{dE_{g,i}^{nm}}{dt} = \begin{cases} \alpha \xi_r (-E_{g,i}^{nm} + aE_i) & \text{for } aE_i > E_{g,i}^{nm} \\ \alpha \xi_r (-E_{g,i}^{nm} + E_i) & \text{for } E_i < E_{g,i}^{nm} \end{cases} [16]$
Thermal strain	Noll's theorem	$\mathbf{F}_{thermal} = \gamma(\theta)\mathbf{I} \text{ for } \gamma(\theta) = \exp\left(\int_{\theta_0}^{\theta} \alpha(s)ds\right) [18]$

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Preparation of SMP and SMPC

Figures 2 and 3 describe the procedure of fabricating SMPs and SMPCs. SMPs and CNT-SMPCs were prepared using an epoxy resin (Epofix®; Struers, Denmark), a curing agent (Jeffamine® D-230; Huntsman, USA), and multi-walled carbon nanotube(MWCNT). The weight fractions of epoxy, curing agent, and MWCNT were 7:2:0 and 7:2:0.5 for SMPs and CNT-SMPs, respectively. After degassing and curing process (110°C for 2hrs), SMP specimen was obtained. For CNT-SMPCs, MWCNT and SMP resin were mixed via tip sonication method, and then the mixture was cast on a hot mould at 130°C for 2hrs.

Figure 2: Schematics for fabrication of SMP

Figure 3: Schematics for fabrication of CNT-SMPC

3.2 Uniaxial thermo-mechanical shape memory tests

Uniaxial thermomechanical behaviors of SMPs and SMPCs were characterized using a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA Q800; TA instruments, Inc.). The range of temperature was set to be between 0°C and 110°C under different temperature rate conditions (3°C/min, 5°C/min, and 7°C/min). Both specimens were deformed by 5% at a rate of 2.5%/min at 110°C, cooled to 0°C while maintaining the deformation, and then unloaded at 0°C. After 10 minutes at unloaded states, specimens were reheated to 110°C for expressing shape memory performance under stress-free conditions. Figure 4 shows shape memory test procedure.

	Mechanical sequence	Temperature
①	Extension the specimen 	High temperature
②	Keep strain 	Cooling
③	Unloading 	Low temperature
④	Heating 	High temperature

Figure 4: Test procedure for uniaxial shape memory test

3.3 Uniaxial thermo-mechanical shape memory tests

Multi-dimensional deformation behaviour of the SMP was measured using a universal testing machine (QUASAR 5; Galdabini, Italy) with an environmental chamber as shown in Figure 5 (a). A flat circular antenna was fabricated to conduct the deployment test. The deployment experiments were carried out following the procedure of a reference [7] under various temperature rate conditions (3°C/min, 5°C/min, and 7°C/min) (Figure 5 (b)). The angle of the antenna during the course of these four steps was measured using a digital camera.

Figure 5. Deployment device and experiments of SMPs and SMPCs: (a) folding device and universal testing machine equipped with heating chamber and (b) schematic of the deployment test

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Material parameters of SMP and SMPC were obtained systematically using isothermal tests and some assumptions. With these properties, firstly uniaxial thermo-mechanical cyclic of the SMP and SMPC was simulated to validate the newly developed constitutive model, whose results were compared with experiments. Then, self-deployable antenna was tested to verify the model under three-dimensional deformation condition.

4.1 Uniaxial thermo-mechanical shape memory behavior

Figure 6 compares the thermo-mechanical behavior of SMP and SMPCs at different temperature rate condition. Both shape memory behavior of SMPs and SMPCs seemed to be not significantly different. However, due to thermally rate behavior of SMPCs, the recovery speed shows meaningful difference between SMPs and SMPCs.

Figure 6. Comparison of thermo-mechanical behavior of SMP and SMPCs at different temperature rate condition: (a) Engineering strain-time and (b) Engineering stress-time

Figure 7 compares experimental and modeling results of the uniaxial thermo-mechanical shape memory test for SMPCs at different temperature rate condition. The new constitutive model can describe the uniaxial shape memory behavior of SMPCs under different temperature rate conditions with high accuracy. Especially, due to the viscoplastic component and thermally affected components (thermal strain and volume fraction of glassy phase), the newly developed constitutive model can describe a tendency of peak of stress and recovery behavior at different temperature rates. Further mechanical simulation results and discussion of CNT-SMPCs will be provided in detail at the conference.

Figure 7. Experimental and modeling results of the uniaxial thermo-mechanical shape memory test for SMPCs: (a) Engineering strain-time and (b) Engineering stress-time

4.2 Multi-dimensional deployment behavior

Multi-dimensional deployment tests for SMPs were simulated and compared to experimental data under different temperature rates (3°C/min, 5°C/min, and 7°C/min). For self-deployable antenna experiments, the changes of the shape memory polymer antenna were recorded and evaluated using a

digital image correlation (DIC) system. Figure 8 (a) shows the results of the angle changes over time at different temperature rates. For evaluating three-dimensional shape changes, the simulation results of 3D shapes were compared with experimental antenna shapes (Figure 8 (b)). The simulation results show all the three-dimensional shape changes of the antenna over time, and has good agreement with the experimental results.

Figure 8: Experimental and modeling results of the multi-dimensional deployment test for SMPs; (a) The angle changes of antenna over time for various temperature rates: each color represents temperature rates (Black: 7°C/min, Red: 5°C/min, and Blue: 3°C/min respectively), (b) 3D shape changes of shape memory antenna over time for 5°C/min

5 CONCLUSIONS

A new three-dimensional constitutive model for simulating the shape memory behaviour of SMPs and CNT-SMPCs was developed considering temperature rate dependency. Materials parameters for the model were systematically obtained using a series of experiments. The constitutive model was successfully implemented into COMSOL software. 3D deformation behaviour of SMP and SMPC antenna at various temperature rate conditions was simulated and compared with experiments, validating the newly developed constitutive equation.

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